

Table 1. Effect of humic acid on growth of rice. West Bengal, India, 1988 wet season.

Treatment ^a	Root dry weight (g/m ²)		Top dry weight (g/m ²)		Tillers/m ² (no.)		Plant height (cm)	
	Maximum tillering	Panicle initiation	Panicle initiation	Flowering	Panicle initiation	Flowering	Panicle initiation	Flowering
Untreated control (only NPK)	21.5	31.2	188	432	419	407	52.2	80.7
NPK + SD in HA @ 25 ml/liter of water	25.6	38.4	238	485	459	447	55.8	84.4
NPK + SD + FS of HA @ 1 ml/ liter of water	24.2	46.2	252	530	495	480	56.4	86.4
NPK + SD + FS of HA + FS of urea 2%	20.9	48.1	243	547	483	460	55.0	84.0
NPK + SD + SA of HA @ 5 liters/ha	28.1	52.2	250	551	523	469	57.9	84.3
NPK + SD + SA of HA @ 10 liters/ha	32.5	60.3	263	579	554	502	59.5	87.2
NPK + SD + SA of HA @ 15 liters/ha	37.9	66.7	255	614	535	553	56.7	86.9
NPK + SD + SA of HA @ 20 liters/ha	31.1	57.1	200	562	467	480	55.5	85.0
LSD (0.05)	3.5	7.8	48.9	56.5	33.7	38.4	3.7	ns

^aSD = Seedling root dipping in humic acid solution (HA), FS = foliar spray, SA = soil application. All plots received 60-13-25 kg NPK/ha.

K/kg, and pH 7.4. Three application methods were tested (Table 1). The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with three replications. Plot size was 15 m².

All plots received 60-13-25 kg NPK/ha as urea, single superphosphate, and muriate of potash.

All the P and K and 1/2 the N and soil-applied humic acid were applied as basal; 1/2 the N and soil-applied humic acid were topdressed in equal splits at maximum tillering and panicle initiation. Foliar spray of humic acid and urea were applied in equal splits at tillering and panicle initiation. MW10 (25 d old) was transplanted 27 Jul and harvested 16 Oct.

Root-dipped seedlings produced more effective tillers and filled grains/panicle and significantly higher grain and straw yields than the control

Table 2. Effect of humic acid on yield components and grain and straw yield of rice. West Bengal, India, 1988 wet season.

Treatment	Effective tillers (no./m ²)	Filled grains (no./panicle)	1000-grain wt (g)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Straw yield (t/ha)	Harvest index
Untreated control (only NPK)	335	67	21.4	2.3	2.4	49
NPK + SD in HA @ 25 ml/liter of water	385	76	21.9	2.6	3.0	46
NPK + SD + FS of HA @ 1 ml/liter of water	407	79	21.8	2.6	3.1	46
NPK + SD + FS of HA + FS of urea 2%,	383	77	22.2	2.6	3.1	45
NPK + SD + SA of HA @ 5 liters/ha	425	78	21.8	2.8	3.2	46
NPK + SD + SA of HA @ 10 liters/ha	453	84	22.4	2.9	3.3	46
NPK + SD + SA of HA @ 15 liters/ha	487	93	22.3	3.1	3.6	46
NPK + SD + SA of HA @ 20 liters/ha	443	83	22.1	3.0	3.4	48
LSD (0.05)	73	6	0.4	0.3	0.5	ns

(Table 1,2). Root-dipping + soil application of humic acid resulted in better growth, yield-attributing characters, and yields than root-dipping only. With soil-applied humic acid, 15 liters/ha produced the best growth and yield attributes. Root-dipping + soil application of 15 liters

humic acid/ha produced the highest grain and straw yields.

Further study is needed regarding the influence of humic acid on physical properties of soil and on the chemical reactions and biological activity in the soil. □

Influence of potassium-kinetin synergism on rice grain weight

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We studied the effect of four levels of K and four levels of kinetin on 1,000-grain weight of cultivar Triveni during summer 1987. Soil was sandy loam with pH 4.5 and 84.3-13.6-63.8 ppm available NPK. Treatments are given in

Potassium-kinetin interaction on 1000-grain weight of cultivar Triveni at Karamana, India, 1987.

Kinetin level	1000-grain wt (g) at given K ₂ O (kg/ha) level				Mean 1000-grain wt (g)
	No K	17.5	35	70	
0 (water spray)	22.4	23.4	24.8	26.1	24.2
10 ppm at flowering	22.7	23.8	25.6	26.8	24.7
10 ppm 10 d after flowering (DF)	22.7	24.1	26.1	27.0	25.0
10 ppm at flowering + 10 DF	23.2	24.9	26.7	27.0	25.4
Mean	22.7	24.1	25.8	26.7	
	SEM±		LSD (0.05)		
K	0.074		0.215		
B	0.074		0.215		
K × B	0.148		0.430		

the table. The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with three replications.

Grain weight increased with levels of K. Kinetin also improved grain weight—two sprayings resulted in the highest grain weight.

The potassium-kinetin interaction was significant: plants treated with 70 kg K₂O/ha plus a single spray of 10 ppm kinetin at 10 d after flowering produced heavier grains. □

Effect on rice of partial substitution of N by azolla

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We studied azolla as a N substitute for rice in 1985 and 1986 wet seasons. Soil was clayey with pH 7.5, 0.59% organic C, 0.047% total N, 9.0 kg available P/ha, and 315 kg available K/ha. All plots received 22 kg P/ha through single superphosphate at puddling. Rice variety GR11 was grown both years. Azolla alone and azolla with different N levels (10 treatments) were laid out in a randomized block design with four replications (see table). N as urea was

Effect of azolla plus N on rice yield. Navsari, India, 1985 and 1986 wet seasons.

Treatment	Yield (t/ha)		
	1985	1986	Mean
One crop azolla incorporated	2.9	2.0	2.9
Two crops azolla incorporated	3.2	2.9	3.1
Three crops azolla incorporated	3.4	3.1	3.2
One crop azolla not incorporated	3.7	3.2	3.4
30 kg N/ha	3.5	3.0	3.2
60 kg N/ha	4.1	3.3	3.7
100 kg N/ha	4.5	4.1	4.3
30 kg N/ha + 1 crop azolla incorporated	3.9	3.8	3.9
60 kg N/ha + 1 crop azolla incorporated	5.2	3.9	4.6
No azolla, no N	2.8	2.7	2.8
LSD (0.05)	0.6	0.7	0.6

applied in two equal splits: at transplanting and 20 d after transplanting. Azolla was surface applied at 300 g/m², allowed to grow for 25 d, then incorporated.

Azolla alone was not effective. Yields were better with azolla + N than with N alone. Yield with 60 kg N/ha + one azolla crop statistically equaled yield with 100 kg N/ha without azolla: incorporation of one azolla crop saved about 40% of inorganic N. □

Response of rice to sources, methods, and levels of N

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We studied the effect of three N fertilizers applied using different methods and at different N levels on IR36 in the northeastern Ghat region of Orissa. Soil was sandy loam with pH 5.6, 0.35% organic C, 0.03% total N, CEC 6.5 meq/100 g, 18 ppm available P (Olsen), and 105 ppm available K (NH₄OAC extractable). Uniform 25 kg K/ha was applied as basal through muriate of potash; P was not added

because available P was high.

Urea and large granule urea (LGU) were broadcast in two and three splits; urea supergranules (USG) were placed manually at 8-10 cm depth between rows, 8 d after transplanting. The experiment was laid out in a random block design with three replications. Seedlings were transplanted at 20- × 10-cm spacing.

N application significantly increased grain yield (see table). Yield increased with each increment of N, irrespective of source and method of application. USG recorded the lowest number of tillers/hill, panicles/hill, panicle length, and test weight.

The terraced, 2% slope of the field plus the porous sandy loam soil warranted irrigation at intervals of 3-4 d. N from USG applied all at basal might have been subjected to greater percolation and volatilization losses, resulting in lower efficiency. At 30 and 60 kg N/ha, urea recorded the highest yield attributes, but at 90 kg N/ha, LGU had the highest. At each N level, yields were similar.

Highest return was with LGU at 90 kg N/ha. USG recorded lower returns at all N levels because of its high application cost combined with lower efficiency. □

Influence of source, method, and level of N on grain and straw yields, yield attributes, and returns. NE Orissa, India.

Treatment ^a	Straw yield (t/ha)	Grain yield		Tillers (no./hill)	Panicles (no./hill)	Panicle length (cm)	1000-grain wt (g)	Returns (\$/ha)
		t/ha	% increase					
No N	2.0	2.2	—	8.0	7.2	17.6	18.9	50.0
30 kg N/ha								
As urea in 2 splits	3.2	3.1	41.7	12.0	8.5	18.0	19.5	182.0
As USG	3.2	2.8	26.5	9.1	7.5	17.8	19.1	118.7
As LGU in 2 splits	3.1	3.0	36.4	9.8	7.8	17.9	19.4	163.3
60 kg N/ha								
As urea in 3 splits	3.2	3.5	59.1	13.1	9.5	18.3	19.8	222.7
As USG	2.9	3.1	40.1	12.2	9.2	18.0	19.5	135.3
As LGU in 3 splits	3.3	3.3	50.0	13.0	9.3	18.1	19.6	194.0
90 kg N/ha								
As urea in 3 splits	4.2	4.1	85.6	14.0	10.2	18.4	20.2	303.6
As USG	3.4	3.4	56.8	13.5	10.1	18.2	19.7	181.7
As LGU in 3 splits	4.2	4.3	94.8	14.6	11.5	18.5	20.5	331.9
LSD (0.05)	0.2	0.2	—	0.75	0.23	0.23	0.40	—

^a2 splits = broadcast at transplanting and at tillering; 3 splits = broadcast at transplanting, at tillering, and at panicle initiation.

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